

**MALE DOMINATION AND NEW FEMALE IDENTITY: A
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FAY WELDON'S *PRAXIS* AND NAMITA
GOKHALE'S *PARO: DREAMS OF PASSION***

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ABSTRACT

The novels of women writers consist of the latent burning issues related with women as well as those issues that exist in the society since long. Through their writings they have depicted the urges, dreams, desires, sufferings and frustrations of women. Writers like Kamala Markandaya, Ruth Praver Jhabvala, Anita Desai, Gita Mehta, Namita Gokhale, Shashi Deshpande, Shobha De, Arundhati Roy, Manju Kapur et al have successfully captured the Indian ethos. The themes mostly dealt by them include clash between modernity and tradition, identity crisis, search for independence etc. Fay Weldon, an English writer is known for her liberal feminism. Her novel Praxis centres around the character of Praxis who since her childhood has seen her mother, Lucy being abused and beaten-up by her father, Ben Duveen. Praxis throughout her life is forced to suffer at the hands of her male counterparts. Ours is a male dominated society and men often view 'female body' as a site for violence and oppression. Even Praxis feels that the body of a woman is not more than a chunk of flesh where male can feast over ethically and unethically. Namita Gokhale on the contrary, is a novelist of revolutionary zeal. Her women in general and Paro of Paro : Dreams of Passion in particular have evolved and emerged as 'New Women'. They are independent, decisive, determined, self-assertive and dignified; they do not depend on men for strength and survival. They know what they want from life and strive towards achieving their goals with courage and determination. Gokhale's maiden novel Paro : Dreams of Passion is a frank exposition of decadent life style of the urban and suburban Indians. Paro, the central character of the novel has been depicted as a strong-willed woman defying the patriarchal norms of the society and taking several bold steps to establish her identity. Her need for self-discovery, self-expression and self-fulfilment has made her question the very fabric of the patriarchal society which undermines her individuality. The present paper intends to make a comparative study of two novels – Praxis on the one hand and Paro : Dreams of Passion on the other. In the former the protagonist suffers from the crucifixion of the 'feminine sensibility' and the 'feminine-self' whereas in the latter Paro, in search for self revolts against the social and moral codes assigned to women .

Keywords : Frustrations; Suffering; Identity Crisis; Liberal Feminism; Female Body; Patriarchal Society.

Gender perspective in literature has been a great issue which emphasises the importance of the social construction of the gender and the assignment of specific roles which a society provides to different members of the society. Gender and literature are very closely related to each other in the sense that neither can be conceived apart from society and culture. Unlike sex, gender is a social and cultural construct. The sex differences do not imply sexual inequality and male dominance. Yet in a patriarchal social set up masculinity is associated with superiority whereas femininity is linked with inferiority and while masculinity implies strength, action, self assertion and domination, femininity implies weakness, passivity, docility, obedience and self-negation. Moreover, one is incomplete in the absence of the other. Ours is a patriarchal society and females have always been assigned a secondary place in society in relation to male; they play different roles—as a wife, mother, sister and daughter. Since childhood she has been busy fulfilling every wish and every desire of the members of her family but herself does not allow to achieve her individuality and self respect. Man suffers with male-superiority that looks the woman down and makes man absolute and woman 'subject', a silent sufferer.

Most of the Indian writers writing in English especially women writers have depicted the urges, dreams, desires, sufferings and frustration of women. Their writings consist of the latest burning issues related with women as well as those issues that exist in the society since long. Writers like Kamala Markandaya, Ruth Praver Jhabvala, Anita Desai, Gita Mehta, Namita Gokhale, Shashi Deshpande, Shobha De, Arundhati Roy, Manju Kapur, et al. have successfully captured the Indian ethos. They mainly dealt with the themes related to clash between tradition and modernity, identity crisis, search for independence etc.

Fay Weldon, an English writer is known for her liberal feminism. Her novel *Praxis* centres around the character of Praxis who since her childhood has seen her mother Lucy being abused, beaten-up and is raped by her husband Ben Duveen. It is her body that is appreciated by Ben. Her body is the combat field to show the abhorrence of the Jew for Christianity and “his forcible entry into her body, despite her physical protestations and struggle became the vehicle of his victorious conquest over her being the ultimate test of his superior strength, the triumph of his manhood.” (Brownmiller 1975 : 14) Praxis witnessed her mother’s helplessness as a victim of marital rape in the childhood when she finds her father’s masculinity overpowers her mother’s femininity wrapped in physical and verbal assault :

He seizes her hair, pulls back her head. He is strong : she is helpless; if he wishes to rape her, he could, he would. It is in the air. (*Praxis* 1978 : 13)

The raped and traumatized conditions of Lucy lead to the development of confusion and a threat in Praxis regarding the body of a woman. As a child Praxis was not able to understand the exact suffering of her mother. But when she attained her puberty and bled for the first time, she found a striking resemblance with her mother’s destiny as a victim of rape and a victim of being a woman. Rape is a sexual act that is seen as a potent tool to overpower, control and put women in their place by men. Men have been using sexual violence and rape

as a means to wield control over women from time immemorial. When it comes to marital relationships, many men consider themselves the sole owner of their wives and their bodies and would go to any extent to assert their right.

The scenario of man's obsession with the female body continues when Praxis attains maturity. Lucy's madness leads her to live in an asylum leaving Praxis and her elder sister Hypatia alone. Her closeness with Miss Leonard reveals the horror of being raped during the war time. Rape at the war zone "reveals the male psyche in its boldest form, without the veneer of 'chivalry' or civilization. (Brownmiller , 33) Miss Leonard's dream of being loved by man gets shattered and her innocent love is being changed to whoredom when she is raped by father and son both at the same time. She wanted to be loved and appreciated but she faced the cruel animal desire of man. After such traumatized incidents she finds her body very "dirty... could not even talk about it."(Praxis ,71) : Creation of any identity – masculine or feminine – rests mainly upon the patterns of power structures that exist in a society. The Indian male is largely exposed to a set of beliefs in which male supremacy is much alleged and female subjugation is taken for granted. Men are always in a position to oppress women in any familial role they play like father, husband and brother. Another important aspect of the masculine identity is his sexuality. Anjali Arora has rightly said, "the male sexuality is seen as a sign of strength whereas the female sexuality is considered a taboo." (Arora 1999 : 122)

Praxis also becomes a victim of rape. She was raped by Phillip in her drunken state. For him, Praxis was just a body to feast on for the gratification of sexual desire. Praxis, after the incidence had experiences which she never had; it creates a kind of sexual desire in her. She now wants to spend her life with him as she took Phillip's action as a symbol of love for a female body. However Phillip does not think seriously about the relationship between the two. She tries Willie too but he also fails to fulfil her wishes; he uses her for his own selfish needs. Ultimately she gets herself involved in prostitution. With the passage of time Praxis's life takes a turn as everybody – Willie, Hypatia leave her. But Praxis by virtue of her courage moves on in her life without thinking about her past. She later got married to Ivor and had two kids – Robert and Claire. But the happiness was short lived. Her past intervened and her present married life broke up.

Namita Gokhale's *Paro : Dreams of Parsian* is a frank exposition of decadent life style of the urban and suburban Indians. It depicts business class politicians and ladies of metropolitan cities who in the name of modernity and emancipation take undue advantage of the freedom and spoil themselves. Gokhale's works mirror the period, the society in which he lives. She is a writer who is concerned with society; she writes what she witnesses in society. Paro, the central character is a modern woman who spoils herself in search of meaning.

Paro, the central character of the novel is portrayed as a rebel who revolts against the social and moral codes assigned to woman. In an attempt to find the meaning of self, she exploits herself and uses sex as a weapon to gain her hold in the world, but even after exploiting herself Paro finds it impossible to overcome the mental, economic and emotional slavery. Paro marries B.R., the manufacturer and owner of Sita Sewing Machine but this does not last long. After six months she moves towards Bucky 'Bhandpur' who is a little younger to her. Very soon she leaves Bucky too:

Every relationship and encounter seemed to have ended in bitterness, misunderstanding and wrangling. (Gokhale 1999 : 29)

Later she develops an illicit relationship with Suresh, Priya's husband. She talks frankly about sex and complexities of life. In search of perfection and newness, she runs from one man to another.

Paro considers herself a free woman, a symbol and a proto-type of emancipation and individuality :

I am myself - and no one else. Depend on nobody. I am my own person. (48)

There was a time when women enjoyed equal status with men, but slowly a change came and women were supposed to confine within the four walls of the house. With the passage of time women started questioning; they raised their voice against dual standards and the hostile environment of the society. The demand for equality, rightful place, recognition and respect spurred a search for self- fulfilment. Paro's relationship with Avinendra was good earlier but late she gets frustrated and attempts to commit suicide :

Paro lay on the bed, quite inert. Blood dripped from her wrists to little puddles on the floor (56)

Indeed, she suffers a lot as no relationship can survive without commitment. A woman needs inner fulfillment, a companionship, love and protection in her relationship. Paro, in search of pure love makes new relations, but nowhere finds perfection and meaning. Like a politician leaving one party and joining the other, Paro leaves one man and joins the other. She comes in contact with Shambhu Nath Mishra, a member of Congress Party but here too she receives the same treatment. She is 'seduced, used and thrown', leaving her totally disappointed and frustrated :

Paro was again without a man in her life; there was stillness, a lull stagnation. (100)

For the time being she develops her relationship with Suresh, Priya's husband. But very soon realizes her mistake and claims :

I'm doing it in an attempt to, you know, find myself. I mean, I've spent the last umpteen years fucking the men in my life and getting fucked myself in the process. (109)

Namita Gokhale by depicting the character of Paro has tried to draw our attention towards social values and changing image of women in the name of pseudo modernity. Paro represents sexual indulgence amongst the westernised urban Indians. She enjoys freedom like a male without caring for moral values. Male sexuality and sexual behaviour is acceptable and even celebrated as it is a symbol of masculinity, but as far as female sexuality is concerned it is restricted as ours is a patriarchal society and we cannot even think of giving

our women much liberty. Priya, the narrator protagonist belongs to a typical middle class family. She has been a victim of gender discrimination and so could not complete her college education. She wants to liberate herself from her tedious middle class suburban existence :

Suffused with shame and contempt for the poverty and meanness around me I would vow to rise from that mire (14)

Though he marries Suresh who provides her every possible material pleasure there is no emotional fulfilment. Men usually regard women as a sex toy, seducing and using her whenever they wish. Priya has rightly observed :

Sex had become to him, more than a sport, it was a duty, a vocation, a calling. I sensed that it was with sex alone that he reached out to the world. I do not think he ever refused a woman; it was as though he was bound by his code of honour, to ravish every female that he encountered. (40)

Namita Gokhale depicts frankly the psyche of her female protagonists. She in a way exposes the promiscuity prevalent in modern society. Paro represents love-sick modern woman who longs for pure love and fulfilment but fails to get; Priya too does not get emotional fulfilment from any corner.

The present study makes a comparative study of two novels - Fay Weldon's *Praxis* and Namita Gokhale's *Paro : Dreams of Passion*. In the novels the writers have tried to expose the shallowness of the patriarchal norms of the society. Female bodies are viewed only as sites for violence and oppression. Praxis suffers the crucifixion of the feminine sensibility and the feminine self. She has to bear the tag of a whore during the formative and crucial period of her life. Paro, too becomes a victim of the patriarchal society. Though she takes several bold steps to establish her identity, her need for self-discovery, self-expression and self- fulfilment has made her question the very fabric of the patriarchal society which undermines her individuality. However in both the cases it is the woman who is sacrificed and tossed up by the patriarchal society.

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